

A CNN-Transformer Architecture for Mental Stress Classification Using Electroencephalogram Signals

Mejbah Md Fahim¹, Shahriar Nafis¹, Sapnil Sarker Bipro¹,
Mohammad Abdul Motin^{1*}

¹Department of Electrical & Electronic Engineering, Rajshahi University of Engineering & Technology, Kazla, Rajshahi, 6204, Bangladesh.

*Corresponding author(s). E-mail(s): mamotin@eee.ruet.ac.bd;
Contributing authors: mejbah.ruet.eee@gmail.com;
shahriarnafis1969@gmail.com; sapnilsarker123@gmail.com;

Abstract

Mental stress is a growing phenomenon that negatively impacts people's mental and physical health. Different stressful conditions affect different regions of the brain, altering the shapes and frequencies of electroencephalography (EEG), and analyzing these signals provide a non-invasive technique for stress classification. Traditional EEG-based stress classification methods often rely on time-consuming and error-prone hand-crafted feature extraction, which frequently fails to capture the complex, nonlinear pattern of EEG data. To address these challenges, this study presents a deep learning model that directly analyzes the raw EEG signals using convolutional neural networks (CNNs) and transformer encoders to classify different stages of stress. The model was evaluated using two publicly available datasets: STEW and SAM40. It achieved 96.59% accuracy for binary classification and 97.05% for three-class classification on the STEW dataset, along with 96.19% for binary classification and 96.56% for three-class classification on the SAM40 dataset. Although there were different stimuli, data collection protocols, and variations in sensors across these datasets, the model showed state-of-the-art performance. This highlights the applicability of the model to focus on early intervention of stress and improving stress monitoring using a wearable device.

Keywords: Mental Stress Monitoring, Electroencephalogram, Wearable Technology, Cognitive Load Analysis, Convolutional Neural Network, Transformer

1 Introduction

Stress represents an instability-causing factor that disrupts equilibrium, making it harder for an individual to respond to environmental demands while maintaining physiological balance [1]. As a result, stress triggers biological changes that lead to adaptive behavior. Real-world stress reactions rely on two critical elements: unmanageable events and unpredictable situations that are beyond the individual's control [2]. Modern studies adopt the definition of psychological stress by Lazarus et al. [3], who explain it as a person's feeling that the demands around them are too much to manage, potentially affecting their physical and mental health. Studies indicate that stress affects more than 70% of Americans who face elevated health risks due to cancer, cardiovascular diseases, depression, and diabetes [4]. Chronic stress causes damage to the immune system functioning and mental health. Therefore, early intervention can help individuals regain control and avoid the progression of stress-related illnesses [5]. Stress detection techniques can be categorized into subjective, physiological, and neurophysiological approaches. EEG is widely used as a neurophysiological method for stress detection [6]. EEG is an effective way to find stress because it records brain activity directly and shows how the autonomic nervous system is out of balance when an individual is stressed. Researchers observe changes in brain wave patterns to monitor cognitive and emotional states [7–10]. As a result, EEG is considered as an effective tool for scientific investigation and clinical practice [11].

Machine learning (ML) and deep learning (DL) techniques have been widely used to analyze EEG signals for mental stress detection in previous studies. Hosseini et al. [10] developed an emotional stress recognition system using EEG signals. The Elman classifier was used to identify two emotional states with an 82.7% accuracy. Al-Shargie et al. [12] aimed to detect mental stress from EEG signals. The EEG signals were collected at a sampling frequency of 256 Hz over 40-second intervals to differentiate between stress and rest during mental arithmetic tasks, and using the support vector machine (SVM) classifier, they achieved 80% accuracy. Jun et al. [13] developed an automatic stress recognition method using EEG-based features such as relative differences in beta and alpha power, achieving accuracies of 75% in three-class stress classification and 96% in the binary classification. Shon et al. [14] used the genetic algorithm for feature selection and a k-NN classifier on the DEAP dataset, employing statistical, Hjorth, band power, and frontal alpha asymmetry features, achieving 71.76% accuracy. Jebelli et al. [15] proposed a stress detection system for construction workers based on EEG signal recordings. Laboratory technicians collect EEG data, and a Gaussian SVM with fixed windowing was used, achieving 80.32% classification accuracy. AlShorman et al. [16] examined EEG frontal lobe spectrum analysis to detect stress. An FFT-based power density feature extraction yielded an accuracy of 98.21% utilizing SVM and Naive Bayes classifiers. Several research studies from the past few years analyzed EEG-based stress detection through machine learning, but such work faces manual feature extraction. To overcome the shortcomings, we proposed a convolutional neural network (CNN) and a transformer encoder-based deep learning model to classify different stress levels. The contributions of this work are as follows:

1. A deep learning framework combining CNNs with transformer encoders is proposed to classify stress levels based on EEG signals.
2. The proposed model is evaluated using two publicly available EEG datasets and exhibits state-of-the-art performance.
3. The performance of the binary and three-class stress classification is compared with previous studies.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. The proposed method used in the research to achieve our objectives is presented in Section 2, while the experimental results are demonstrated in Section 3. The discussion of the results obtained through classification, statistical analysis, and comparison with previous methods is presented in Section 4. Finally, the work is concluded in Section 5.

2 Methodology

2.1 Datasets

Two publicly available datasets were used to evaluate the proposed methodology. The demographic information for both datasets is described below.

2.1.1 STEW Dataset

The STEW dataset contains EEG recordings from 48 participants. They used a scale of 1 to 9 to rate their level of mental stress after every task. Subjects 5, 24, and 42 were excluded from the data set due to the absence of ratings. The Emotiv EPOC device was employed to record EEG signals at a sampling rate of 128 Hz, with 14 channels (AF3, F7, F3, FC5, T7, P7, O1, O2, P8, T8, FC6, F4, F8, AF4) [17]. Participants performed an audio response task that was based on the Vienna Test System and compared items between two display panels. Subjects were seated 60 cm from a 24-inch LED screen during the resting condition, and they were not required to perform any tasks. The SIMKAP test was conducted to obtain EEG data for the stress condition. In order to mitigate transition effects, the initial and final 15 seconds of each recording were eliminated, resulting in a total of 2 minutes and 30 seconds of useful information per subject.

2.1.2 SAM40 Dataset

The SAM40 dataset consists of EEG recordings from 40 subjects (14 females, 26 males; mean age: 21.5 years) participating in an arithmetic exercise to evaluate cognitive stress. Following each experiment, participants rated their stress levels on a scale from 1 to 10. Electroencephalogram (EEG) data were acquired via Emotiv EPOC Flex Gel Kit, comprising 32 channels (Cz, Fz, Fp1, F7, F3, FC1, C3, FC5, FT9, T7, CP5, CP1, P3, P7, PO9, O1, Pz, Oz, O2, PO10, P8, P4, CP2, CP6, T8, FT10, FC6, C4, FC2, F4, F8, FP2) at a sampling frequency of 128 Hz [18]. During the exercise, participants looked at arithmetic problems and gave a thumbs-up or thumbs-down gesture to show if the answer was correct or not. There were three trials for each person, and each trial

included six questions of varying difficulty. The task was completed in 25 seconds per trial, with a 5-second rest interval between trials to reduce the effects of transition.

2.2 Data Preprocessing and Data Segmentation

The data was segmented into a length of 512 samples with an overlap of 128 samples. The total number of samples was 6615 for STEW and 2640 for the SAM40 dataset. A Savitzky-Golay filter was used to eliminate baseline drift. The same windowing technique was used for data preparation. For both datasets, the 14 common EEG channels were used in the study.

2.3 Transformer Encoder-based CNN model

The proposed deep learning model uses 1D-CNNs and transformer encoders to capture spatial and sequential features in EEG signals for classification.

Fig. 1 A transformer encoder-based CNN model is used to detect stress levels. Two different inputs, such as STEW and SAM40, are used to train the model. Here, the CNN model extracts the temporal and advanced spatial features, and the encoder is used to avoid long-term dependencies. The optimizer in the output layer is sigmoid for binary classification, and for three-label multi-class, it is softmax.

2.3.1 Convolutional Feature Extraction

The proposed framework consists of three 1D-CNN layers, each of which is followed by a max pooling layer, as shown in Figure 1. The initial layer has 64 filters, each with a size of 3 and a stride of 1, with a rectified linear unit (ReLU) activation function. The same stride and filter size are used in the second and third layers, which employ 128 and 512 filters.

2.3.2 Positional Embedding and Tokenization

In this study, we use learnable positional embeddings into the reshaped output of the final 1D-CNN layer. This maintains the order of the EEG signal segments before they

Table 1 The 1D-CNN and transformer encoder model parameters

Block	Layer Name	Binary Classification		3 Label Classification	
		Output Shape	Parameter	Output Shape	Parameter
CNN Block	Input Layer	(None, 512, 14)	0	(None, 512, 14)	0
	Conv1D	(None, 512, 64)	2,752	(None, 512, 64)	2,752
	MaxPooling1D	(None, 256, 64)	0	(None, 256, 64)	0
	Conv1D	(None, 256, 128)	24,704	(None, 256, 128)	24,704
	MaxPooling1D	(None, 128, 128)	0	(None, 128, 128)	0
	Conv1D	(None, 128, 512)	197,120	(None, 128, 512)	197,120
	MaxPooling1D	(None, 64, 512)	0	(None, 64, 512)	0
	Reshape	(None, 4, 8192)	0	(None, 4, 8192)	0
Dense	(None, 4, 64)	524,352	(None, 4, 64)	524,352	
Encoder Block 1	Multi-Head Attention	(None, 4, 64)	132,672	(None, 4, 64)	132,672
	Layer Normalization	(None, 4, 64)	128	(None, 4, 64)	128
	Dense	(None, 4, 128)	8,320	(None, 4, 128)	8,320
	Dropout	(None, 4, 128)	0	(None, 4, 128)	0
	Dense	(None, 4, 64)	8,256	(None, 4, 64)	8,256
	Layer Normalization	(None, 4, 64)	128	(None, 4, 64)	128
Encoder Block 2	Multi-Head Attention	(None, 4, 64)	132,672	(None, 4, 64)	132,672
	Layer Normalization	(None, 4, 64)	128	(None, 4, 64)	128
	Dense	(None, 4, 128)	8,320	(None, 4, 128)	8,320
	Dropout	(None, 4, 128)	0	(None, 4, 128)	0
	Dense	(None, 4, 64)	8,256	(None, 4, 64)	8,256
	Layer Normalization	(None, 4, 64)	128	(None, 4, 64)	128
Encoder Block 3	Multi-Head Attention	(None, 4, 64)	132,672	(None, 4, 64)	132,672
	Layer Normalization	(None, 4, 64)	128	(None, 4, 64)	128
	Dense	(None, 4, 128)	8,320	(None, 4, 128)	8,320
	Dropout	(None, 4, 128)	0	(None, 4, 128)	0
	Dense	(None, 4, 64)	8,256	(None, 4, 64)	8,256
	Layer Normalization	(None, 4, 64)	128	(None, 4, 64)	128
Classification	GlobalAveragePooling1D	(None, 64)	0	(None, 64)	0
	Dense	(None, 128)	8,320	(None, 128)	8,320
	Dropout	(None, 128)	0	(None, 128)	0
	Dense	(None, 1)	129	(None, 3)	387
Total parameters			3,617,669		3,618,443

are sent to the transformer encoder. The model preserves critical sequence information by integrating the reshaped regions with positional embeddings.

2.3.3 Transformer Encoder and Attention Layer

The proposed model uses three transformer encoder blocks to further process the tokenized embeddings. The transformer uses self-attention techniques. The transformer encoder is made up of a series of identical layers, each including two sub-layers: multi-head attention (MHA) and a position-wise feed-forward network. Each sub-layer receives residual connections before layer normalization.

The output of the last layer is linearly transformed into three vectors of equal dimensions: query (Q), key (K), and value (V). The attention mechanism calculates the dot product between Q and K , which is scaled by the square root of the dimension d_k . The attention weights are first obtained by passing this result through a softmax function, and they are subsequently multiplied by V to generate the attention output

[19]. Scaled dot-product attention involves queries, keys, and values of dimension d_k and d_v . The dot products between Q and all K vectors are split by $\sqrt{d_k}$, and the resulting scores are normalized using softmax. The attention calculation is usually done over the batched matrices Q , K , and V [20, 21].

$$\text{Output of each sub-layer} = \text{LayerNorm}(x + \text{Sublayer}(x)) \quad (1)$$

where $\text{Sublayer}(x)$ is the function implemented by the sub-layer itself.

$$\text{Attention}(Q, K, V) = \text{softmax}\left(\frac{QK^T}{\sqrt{d_k}}\right)V \quad (2)$$

In the MHA mechanism, the transformer encoder employs eight attention units. Queries, keys, and values are converted from the input embeddings. To mitigate overfitting, each encoder block uses a dropout layer with a rate of 0.1.

2.3.4 Classification and Cross-Validation

The output of the final encoder layer is subjected to global average pooling (GAP). This is followed by a dense layer consisting of 128 neurons, which employs the Gaussian error linear unit (GELU) activation function. A dropout layer with a rate of 0.1 is also implemented during this phase. The predictions are resulted by the final output layer. The Adam optimizer is employed to optimize the model. A sigmoid activation function (Equation 5) is employed together with binary cross-entropy loss (Equation 3) for binary classification. The categorical cross-entropy loss (Equation 4) is implemented with a softmax activation function (Equation 6) for three-class classification.

$$\text{Loss}_{\text{BCE}} = -\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N [y_{(i)} \log(\hat{y}_i) + (1 - y_{(i)}) \log(1 - \hat{y}_i)] \quad (3)$$

$$\text{Loss}_{\text{CCE}} = -\sum_{i=1}^N \sum_{c=1}^C y_{(i,c)} \log(\hat{y}_{(i,c)}) \quad (4)$$

$$\sigma(x) = \frac{1}{1 + e^{-x}} \quad (5)$$

$$\text{Softmax}(x_i) = \frac{e^{x_i}}{\sum_{j=1}^C e^{x_j}} \quad (6)$$

Where Loss_{BCE} is the loss function for binary cross-entropy while Loss_{CCE} is for categorical cross-entropy, \hat{y}_i and $\hat{y}_{(i,c)}$ are predicted labels, as well as $y_{(i)}$ and $y_{(i,c)}$ are true labels, N is the number of samples, C is the number of classes, and x_i is the input to the i^{th} class.

The model is evaluated using 5-fold cross-validation. Each fold undergoes 120 epochs of training with a learning rate of 0.0001 and a batch size of 64. The training is terminated when the validation performance stabilizes using callback functions to implement early stopping with adaptive learning rate adjustment.

2.4 Performance Parameters

Standard classification metrics, such as precision, recall, accuracy, and F1 score, are employed to assess how well the suggested model performs. Precision is the ratio of true positives to the sum of true and false positives, which is calculated as the proportion of correctly predicted positive cases out of all predicted positives (Equation 7). Recall is a metric that shows the model’s capacity to identify all true positive cases. It is calculated by dividing the number of true positives by the total number of actual positives (Equation 8). The F1 score is a harmonic mean that is calculated to reflect the overall classification performance and provides a balanced measure of precision and recall (Equation 9). The ratio of correctly predicted cases to the total number of evaluated cases in the dataset is referred to as accuracy (Equation 10).

$$\textit{Precision} = \frac{\textit{True Positive}}{\textit{True Positive} + \textit{False Positive}} \quad (7)$$

$$\textit{Recall} = \frac{\textit{True Positive}}{\textit{True Positive} + \textit{False Negative}} \quad (8)$$

$$\textit{F1 Score} = \frac{2 \cdot (\textit{Precision} \cdot \textit{Recall})}{\textit{Precision} + \textit{Recall}} \quad (9)$$

$$\textit{Accuracy} = \frac{\textit{True Positive} + \textit{True Negative}}{\textit{True Positive} + \textit{True Negative} + \textit{False Positive} + \textit{False Negative}} \quad (10)$$

3 Results

The proposed method was evaluated using the STEW dataset for binary and three-class stress classification tasks. In binary classification, it scored an average accuracy of 96.59%, a precision of 96.51%, and recall values of 96.56% for low stress and 96.62% for high stress. The mean F1 score was 96.10%. The model achieved an overall accuracy of 97.05% for three-class classification (low, moderate, high). The precision values were 97.64% for low stress, 96.22% for moderate stress, and 97.57% for high stress. Recall varied between 96.62% and 97.70%, while F1 scores ranged from 96.33% to 97.67%.

In the SAM40 dataset, which varies from STEW in terms of subject diversity, EEG signal kinds, and data patterns, the model attained an accuracy of 96.19% in binary classification. Precision was 95.60% for low stress and 96.60% for high stress, with corresponding recall values of 96.80% and 95.00%. F1 scores varied between 95% and 97%. The model achieved an overall accuracy of 96.56% in three-class categorization. The precision for low, moderate, and high stress levels was 97.60%, 95.60%, and 96.40%, respectively, while the recall values were 92.40%, 98.20%, and 95.20%. The mean F1 score was 95.33%.

Fig. 2 (i) Average confusion matrix of 5-fold cross-validation (a) STEW binary classification (b) STEW three-class classification (c) SAM40 binary classification (d) SAM40 three-class classification, (ii) Accuracy vs epochs of 5th fold (a) STEW binary classification (b) STEW three-class classification (c) SAM40 binary classification (d) SAM40 three-class classification.

Table 2 Precision and Recall of the proposed model on both datasets in each fold

Fold	STEW Dataset				SAM40 Dataset			
	Binary		Three-class		Binary		Three-class	
	Precision.	Recall	Precision.	Recall	Precision	Recall	Precision	Recall
1	96.00	96.50	96.67	97.33	96.50	96.50	96.33	96.33
2	95.50	95.50	96.00	96.00	95.50	95.50	96.67	95.67
3	96.00	96.00	97.33	97.33	96.50	96.00	96.67	95.00
4	96.00	96.00	97.00	97.00	96.00	95.50	97.33	95.00
5	97.00	97.50	97.33	97.33	96.00	96.00	95.67	94.33
Avg.	96.10	96.10	97.07	97.07	96.19	95.90	96.53	95.26

Table 3 Performances of the proposed model on both datasets in each fold

Fold	STEW Dataset				SAM40 Dataset			
	Binary		Three-class		Binary		Three-class	
	Acc.	F1	Acc.	F1	Acc.	F1	Acc.	F1
1	96.59	96.50	97.45	97.00	96.59	97.00	96.59	96.00
2	96.07	95.50	97.20	96.33	95.64	95.50	96.59	96.00
3	97.05	95.50	96.60	97.67	96.02	96.00	96.02	96.60
4	97.83	96.00	96.75	97.00	95.83	95.50	96.21	96.00
5	96.37	97.00	97.73	97.33	95.83	95.50	95.64	95.33
Avg.	96.59	96.10	97.05	97.07	96.19	95.90	96.56	95.87

4 Discussion

EEG signals are frequently employed to evaluate cognitive load because of their ability to reflect neural activity associated with mental and emotional processes. A classification framework that integrates CNN with transformer architectures was implemented on the STEW and SAM40 datasets in this analysis. The architecture is supposed to capture the spatial and temporal patterns that are associated with stress-related EEG activity. Differences in data distribution, subject variability, or recording conditions may be a sign of minor variations in classification outcomes across individual records.

Fig. 3 (i) Absolute power distribution using STEW dataset (a) high stress (b) moderate stress (c) low stress, (ii) absolute power distribution using SAM40 dataset (a) high stress (b) moderate stress (c) low stress.

Figure 3 illustrates distinct spatial activity patterns under high, moderate, and low stress levels by presenting EEG power topographic maps across various frequency bands. The interpretation is predicated on the absolute power measurements of both datasets. The STEW dataset indicates that high-stress conditions are represented by lighter color intensities, which shows a higher absolute power across frequency bands. The maps undergo a transition to darker shades (e.g., blue tones) as stress levels decrease, which is indicative of a decrease in absolute power. In contrast, the SAM40 dataset exhibits minimal variation across stress levels. Because the stressor was a light arithmetic activity, participants may not exhibit reliable stress responses, decreasing their capacity to differentiate stress classes.

A comparative summary of the classification performance, datasets, and previous studies is presented in table 4. Participant counts in these tasks varied from five to sixty-four. Lim et al. [17], Sharma et al. [22], and Chakladar et al. [24] employed publicly accessible datasets, including STEW and DEAP, while Hosseini et al. [10], Al-Shargie et al. [12], and Zeng et al. [23] employed private EEG datasets. Traditional machine learning methods, including the Elman network, support vector machines (SVM), and k-nearest neighbors (KNN), were employed in the initial stress classification objectives, resulting in accuracies ranging from 69.2% to 87.88% [10, 12, 14, 17, 26]. Deep learning models, such as CNN, long short-term memory (LSTM), and bidirectional LSTM (BLSTM), along with hybrid approaches, were

Table 4 Comparative Analysis of the Proposed Model

Ref.	Sub.	Dataset (signal)	Methods	Task	Accuracy	Class
Hosseini et al. [10]	15	Private (EEG)	Elman Classifier	Picture induced emotional task	82.7%	2
Al-shargie et al. [12]	12	Private (EEG)	SVM	Montreal Imaging Stress Task (MIST)	80%	2
Shon et al. [14]	32	DEAP (EEG)	KNN	Audiovisual Stimuli	71.76%	2
Jebelli et al. [15]	11	Private	Gaussian SVM	Repetitive daily task	80.32%	2
Jebelli et al. [15]	10	Private	DNN	Construction-related activities at elevated heights	86.62%	2
Lim et al. [17]	45	STEW (EEG)	SVM	Simkap	69.2%	3
Sharma et al. [22]	45	STEW (EEG)	CNN, BLSTM	Simkap	96.77%	2
Sharma et al. [22]	45	STEW (EEG)	CNN, BLSTM	Simkap	95.36%	3
Zeng et al. [23]	10	Private	EEG-Conv	For fatigue drove 2 hours, and for alert	91.78%	2
Zeng et al. [23]	10	Private (EEG)	EEG-conv-R (Residual)	Driving Simulator	92.68%	2
Chakladar et al. [24]	48	Stew (EEG)	BLSTM, LSTM	Simkap	82.57%	3
Dong et al. [25]	17	Private	CNN, LSTM	Show positive and negative pictures	99.12%	2
Sundaresan et al. [26]	13	Private	2layer LSTM	Arithmetic, color, and auditory stimuli	93.27%	4
Sundaresan et al. [26]	13	Private	RNN SVM	Arithmetic, color, and auditory stimuli	87.88%	2
Fernandez et al. [27]	30	Private	LightGBM	puzzles, mathematical tasks and video games	86.77%	2
Fernandez et al. [27]	30	Private	LightGBM	puzzles, mathematical tasks and video games	86.24%	3
Kuanar et al. [28]	25	Private	ConvNet + BLSTM	English Character shown	92.50%	4
Our Work	45	STEW (EEG)	CNN, Transformer	Simkap	96.59%	2
					97.05%	3
	40	SAM40 (EEG)	CNN, Transformer	Solving arithmetic questions	96.19%	2
				96.56%	3	

incorporated into subsequent studies. For instance, Dong et al. [25] achieved a classification accuracy of 99.12% by employing a CNN-LSTM model on private EEG data from 64 individuals. This outcome demonstrates the advantages of deep architectures to obtain the temporal and spatial EEG features, particularly in circumstances of large datasets.

LightGBM models were proposed by Fernandez et al. [27] for the purpose of detecting mental workloads during tasks that involve mathematics and puzzle games. The detection rates for these models exceeded 86%. Although tree-based ensemble models were successful in recognizing workload-related patterns, they generally underperformed in comparison to deep learning methods, particularly when advanced spatial-temporal feature extraction was implemented. The classification performance of single model has been increased by the integration of CNN with residual connections and BiLSTM with LSTM architectures [23, 24]. To be more precise, Sharma et al. [22]

reported that a 1D-CNN combined with BLSTM obtained classification accuracies of 96.77% for binary tasks and 95.36% for three-class tasks.

5 Conclusion

This study introduces a deep learning model for stress classification based on EEG signals. The proposed architecture employs a hybrid framework that integrates CNN with transformer encoder layers. While the CNN component captures local spatial features from the EEG signals, the transformer effectively models long-range temporal dependencies, enabling the network to better interpret stress-related patterns within their sequential context. This combined approach allows the model to simultaneously extract both short-term and long-term features, which is critical for accurate stress pattern recognition. The model was evaluated on two publicly available datasets—STEW and SAM40—achieving accuracy of 96.59% for binary classification and 97.05% for multi-class classification. It achieved an accuracy of 96.19% for binary classification and 96.56% for multi-class classification on the SAM40 dataset. The proposed automated model eliminates the need for manual feature engineering and conventional statistical analysis, thereby enhancing its scalability for real-world applications. This approach demonstrates strong potential for integration into wearable-based systems for mental stress assessment and monitoring.

6 Compliance with Ethical Standards

There are no conflicts of interest. Research uses publicly available deidentified datasets.

References

- [1] Hou, X., Liu, Y., Sourina, O., Tan, Y.R.E., Wang, L., Mueller-Wittig, W.: Eeg based stress monitoring. In: 2015 IEEE International Conference on Systems, Man, and Cybernetics, pp. 3110–3115 (2015). <https://doi.org/10.1109/SMC.2015.540>
- [2] Koolhaas, J.M., Bartolomucci, A., Buwalda, B., Boer, S., Flugge, G., Korte, S.M., Meerlo, P., Murison, R., Olivier, B., Palanza, P., Richter-Levin, G., Sgoifo, A., Steimer, T., Stiedl, O., Dijk, G., Wöhr, M., Fuchs, E.: Stress revisited: A critical evaluation of the stress concept. *Neuroscience and biobehavioral reviews* **35**, 1291–301 (2011) <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neubiorev.2011.02.003>
- [3] Lazarus, R.S., Folkman, S.: *Stress, Appraisal, and Coping*. Springer, New York (1984)
- [4] Cohen, S., Janicki-Deverts, D., Miller, G.E.: Psychological stress and disease. *Jama* **298**(14), 1685–1687 (2007)
- [5] Li, R., Liu, Z.: Stress detection using deep neural networks. *BMC Medical Informatics and Decision Making* **20**, 1–10 (2020)

- [6] Badr, Y., Tariq, U., Al-Shargie, F., Babiloni, F., Al Mughairbi, F., Al-Nashash, H.: A review on evaluating mental stress by deep learning using eeg signals. *Neural Computing and Applications* **36**(21), 12629–12654 (2024)
- [7] Healey, J.A., Picard, R.W.: Detecting stress during real-world driving tasks using physiological sensors. *IEEE Transactions on intelligent transportation systems* **6**(2), 156–166 (2005)
- [8] Kar, S., Bhagat, M., Routray, A.: Eeg signal analysis for the assessment and quantification of driver’s fatigue. *Transportation research part F: traffic psychology and behaviour* **13**(5), 297–306 (2010)
- [9] Henriques, J.B., Davidson, R.J.: Left frontal hypoactivation in depression. *Journal of abnormal psychology* **100**(4), 535 (1991)
- [10] Hosseini, S.A., Khalilzadeh, M.A.: Emotional stress recognition system using eeg and psychophysiological signals: Using new labelling process of eeg signals in emotional stress state. In: *2010 International Conference on Biomedical Engineering and Computer Science*, pp. 1–6 (2010). IEEE
- [11] Sulaiman, N., Taib, M.N., Lias, S., Murat, Z.H., Aris, S.A., Hamid, N.H.A.: Novel methods for stress features identification using eeg signals. *International Journal of Simulation: Systems, Science and Technology* **12**(1), 27–33 (2011)
- [12] Al-Shargie, F., Tang, T.B., Badruddin, N., Kiguchi, M.: Mental stress quantification using eeg signals. In: *International Conference for Innovation in Biomedical Engineering and Life Sciences: ICIBEL2015*, 6-8 December 2015, Putrajaya, Malaysia 1, pp. 15–19 (2016). Springer
- [13] Jun, G., Smitha, K.G.: Eeg based stress level identification. In: *2016 IEEE International Conference on Systems, Man, and Cybernetics (SMC)*, pp. 003270–003274 (2016). IEEE
- [14] Shon, D., Im, K., Park, J.-H., Lim, D.-S., Jang, B., Kim, J.-M.: Emotional stress state detection using genetic algorithm-based feature selection on eeg signals. *International Journal of environmental research and public health* **15**(11), 2461 (2018)
- [15] Jebelli, H., Hwang, S., Lee, S.: Eeg-based workers’ stress recognition at construction sites. *Automation in Construction* **93**, 315–324 (2018)
- [16] AlShorman, O., Masadeh, M., Heyat, M.B.B., Akhtar, F., Almahasneh, H., Ashraf, G.M., Alexiou, A.: Frontal lobe real-time eeg analysis using machine learning techniques for mental stress detection. *Journal of integrative neuroscience* **21**(1), 20 (2022)
- [17] Lim, W.L., Sourina, O., Wang, L.P.: Stew: Simultaneous task eeg workload

- data set. *IEEE Transactions on Neural Systems and Rehabilitation Engineering* **26**(11), 2106–2114 (2018)
- [18] Ghosh, R., Deb, N., Sengupta, K., Phukan, A., Choudhury, N., Kashyap, S., Phadikar, S., Saha, R., Das, P., Sinha, N., *et al.*: Sam 40: Dataset of 40 subject eeg recordings to monitor the induced-stress while performing stroop color-word test, arithmetic task, and mirror image recognition task. *Data in Brief* **40**, 107772 (2022)
- [19] Song, Y., Zheng, Q., Liu, B., Gao, X.: Eeg conformer: Convolutional transformer for eeg decoding and visualization. *IEEE Transactions on Neural Systems and Rehabilitation Engineering* **31**, 710–719 (2022)
- [20] Xie, J., Zhang, J., Sun, J., Ma, Z., Qin, L., Li, G., Zhou, H., Zhan, Y.: A transformer-based approach combining deep learning network and spatial-temporal information for raw eeg classification. *IEEE Transactions on Neural Systems and Rehabilitation Engineering* **30**, 2126–2136 (2022)
- [21] Vaswani, A., Shazeer, N., Parmar, N., Uszkoreit, J., Jones, L., Gomez, A.N., Kaiser, L., Polosukhin, I.: Attention is all you need. *Advances in neural information processing systems* **30** (2017)
- [22] Sharma, V., Ahirwal, M.K.: An end-to-end brain computer interface system for mental workload estimation through hybrid deep learning model. *Human-Centric Intelligent Systems* **4**(4), 599–609 (2024)
- [23] Zeng, H., Yang, C., Dai, G., Qin, F., Zhang, J., Kong, W.: Eeg classification of driver mental states by deep learning. *Cognitive neurodynamics* **12**, 597–606 (2018)
- [24] Chakladar, D.D., Dey, S., Roy, P.P., Dogra, D.P.: Eeg-based mental workload estimation using deep blstm-lstm network and evolutionary algorithm. *Biomedical Signal Processing and Control* **60**, 101989 (2020)
- [25] Dong, J.: Analysis of emotional stress of teachers in japanese teaching process based on eeg signal analysis. *Occupational Therapy International* **2022**(1), 2593338 (2022)
- [26] Sundaresan, A., Penchina, B., Cheong, S., Grace, V., Valero-Cabré, A., Martel, A.: Evaluating deep learning eeg-based mental stress classification in adolescents with autism for breathing entrainment bci. *Brain Informatics* **8**(1), 13 (2021)
- [27] Fernandez, J., Martínez, R., Innocenti, B., López, B.: Contribution of eeg signals for students’ stress detection. *IEEE Transactions on Affective Computing* (2024)
- [28] Kuanar, S., Athitsos, V., Pradhan, N., Mishra, A., Rao, K.R.: Cognitive analysis of working memory load from eeg, by a deep recurrent neural network. In:

Author Biography

Mejbah Md Fahim received his B.Sc. in EEE from *RUET*, Bangladesh, in **2025**. His research interests include deep learning, signal and image processing, and healthcare applications.

Shahriar Nafis received his B.Sc. in EEE from *RUET*, Bangladesh, in **2025**. His research interests include IOT and biomedical signal processing.

Sapnil Sarker Bipro received the B.Sc. in EEE from *RUET*, Bangladesh. His current research interests include DL-based biomedical signal processing. He is the 2nd runner-up of IEEE SP Cup 2024, ICASSP.

Dr. Mohammad Abdul Motin is an Associate Professor at *RUET*, holds a Ph.D. from the University of Melbourne. His research interests include biomedical signal processing, machine learning, and wearable health monitoring.